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3D-Printed stealth honeycomb conductive nanoparticles-filled PEEK thermoplastic resin curve patch composite for enhanced RCS reduction

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I. Introduction

Background

❖ 3D-Printing based RAS (Radar Absorbing Structure)

- FDM (Fused Deposition Modeling) 3D-Printed EM wave absorbing metastructure

< Octet truss based metastructure^[1] >

< Gyroid based metastructure^[2] >

< Dual-nozzle frequency-selective composites^[3] >

- Conventionally fabricated composite RAS

< Hot-press molding processes^[4] >

< Autoclave curing processes^[5] >

< Pattern printing processes^[6] >

[1] D.D.Lim et al. Broadband mechanical metamaterial absorber enabled by fused filament fabrication 3D printing, Additive Manufacturing 55 (2022) 102856
 [2] Q. An et al. A Novel Ultra-Wideband Electromagnetic-Wave-Absorbing Metastructure Inspired by Bionic Gyroid Structures, Adv. Mater. 2023, 35, 2300659
 [3] J.Y.Cho et al. Fusedly Deposited Frequency-Selective Composites Fabricated by a Dual-Nozzle 3D Printing as Microwave Filter, Polymers 2024, 16, 786
 [4] W.H.Jang et al. High-temperature corrugated-core radar stealth Ni-plated glass/ bismaleimide sandwich composites, Composite Structures 365 (2025) 119185
 [5] W.H.Choi et al. Broadband microwave-absorbing honeycomb structure with novel design concept, Composites Part B 83 (2015) 14-20
 [6] S.M.Baek et al. A lightweight, flexible, and polarization-insensitive microwave absorbing honeycomb core using conductive losses in printed periodic pattern, Composites Part A 180 (2024) 108089

Background

❖ *Application of 3D-Printed RAS*

- 3D-Printing for ABDR (Aircraft Battle Damage Repair)

< Replaceable 3D-Printed polymeric hatch for Gripen by Saab^[7] >

- 3D-Printing patch for RCS reduction

< Application of 3D-Printed patch for RCS reduction^[8] >

[7] <https://3dprintingindustry.com/news/saab-trials-3d-printing-to-repair-battle-damaged-gripen-fighter-aircraft-187974>

[8] <https://www.twz.com/29218/these-images-of-an-f-22-raptors-crumbling-radar-absorbent-skin-are-fascinating>

Background

❖ Limitation of conventional thermoplastic for 3D-printing

- Amorphous
 - Impact toughness
 - Dimensional stability
 - Optical transparency
 - Low heat resistance
 - Solvent sensitivity
 - Stress-cranking

- Semi-Crystalline
 - High heat resistance
 - Chemical resistance
 - Good Fatigue strength
 - High shrinkage and warpage
 - Process complexity

Material	Tensile Strength, Yield (MPa)	Tensile Modulus (GPa)	Flexural Strength (MPa)	Flexural Modulus (GPa)	Izod Impact (kJ/m ²)	Glass Transition Temp (°C)	Moisture Content	Printing Temp (°C)	Chemical Resistance
PEEK (Polyetheretherketone)	85 – 95	3.6 - 4.0	100 - 120	3.8 - 4.0	7	143	0.02	360 - 420	Excellent
Ultem 1010 (Polyetherimide)	81	2.77	144	2.82	21	215	0.02	365 - 395	Excellent
PA66 (Polyamide, Nylon)	60 - 80	2.5 - 3.2	100 - 120	2.5 - 3.0	6 - 9	70	2.5	260 - 290	Poor
PC (Polycarbonate)	55 - 65	2.25	90	2.15	8 - 12	143	0.3	260 - 300	Moderate
PLA (Polylactic Acid)	50 - 70	3.0 - 3.6	80 - 100	3.5 - 110	2 - 5	60	0.4	190 - 220	Poor
ABS (Acrylonitrile-Butadiene-Styrene)	40 - 50	2.2 - 4.4	80 - 100	2.0 - 2.3	15 - 25	105	0.4	230 - 260	Poor

3D printed Carbon Black/Polylactic acid composites for microwave absorption

[9] Chengtao Sum et al. Design of functionally gradient metastructure with ultra-broadband and strong absorption, Composites Part B, 280, 2024, 111484

< PLA/CB filament based gradient meta structure >

< Design of gradient metastructure and EM wave absorbing performance >

Effect of annealing on mechanical and electrical properties of 3D printing PEEK/CNT nanocomposites

[10] Xin Ye et al. Effect of annealing and carbon nanotube infill on the mechanical and electrical properties of additively manufactured polyether-ether-ketone nanocomposites via fused filament fabrication, Additive Manufacturing, 59, (2022), 103188

< Preparation process of PEEK/CNT composite filaments >

< Effect of annealing treatment on the interfacial voids >

< Effect of annealing treatment on (a) tensile strength, (b) elastic modulus (c) electrical conductivity >

Research highlights

Manufacturing

Design

Measurement

Mechanical behavior analysis

II. Materials and methods

Material preparation

■ PEEK

- Superior mechanical properties and toughness
- Above 450 °C, primary thermal decomposition occurs this must be taken into account during filament fabrication
- Chemical, thermal resistance

Name	Glass transition temperature (°C)	Melting temperature (°C)	Deposition temperature (°C)	Crystallinity (%)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Young Modulus (GPa)
PEEK	144	340	450	30	100	3.7-4.0

< Chemical structure, thermal and tensile properties of neat PEEK^[11] >

■ Multi-Walled Carbon Nanotubes

- Increase dielectric loss properties
- Increase mechanical properties
- Aggregation due to van der Waals forces
- Viscosity control

Name	Average diameter (nm)	Length (μm)
MWNTs	15-25	5-15

< Dimensional specifications of Multi-Walled Carbon Nanotubes^[12] >

[11] Anouar El Magri et al An overview on the influence of process parameters through the characteristic of 3D-printed PEEK and parts, High Performance Polymers, 2021, 1–19

[12] Shandong Dazhan Nano Materials, GT-304 Technical Data Sheet

Material preparation

❖ PEEK based filament extrude process

< MWNTs dispersion and extrude process >

< SEM images of (a) Neat PEEK, (b) PEEK/MWNTs 12 wt% >

Material preparation

❖ Electromagnetic properties of PEEK/MWNTs nanocomposites

< Complex permittivity of PEEK/MWNTs (a) real part, (b) imaginary part and (c) free space measurement system >

@ 10 GHz	Neat PEEK	PEEK/ MWNTs 3 wt%	PEEK/ MWNTs 6 wt%	PEEK/ MWNTs 9 wt%	PEEK/ MWNTs 12 wt%
Complex permittivity	2.70 - j0.03	6.85 - j1.30	12.77 - j2.67	22.43 - j9.58	29.64 - j38.13
Complex permeability	0.96 - j0.01	0.98 - j0.01	0.98 - j0.01	0.95 - j0.02	0.97 - j0.01

< Complex permittivity and permeability of PEEK/MWNTs at 10 GHz >

Methods

❖ Multilayer radar-absorbing structure

- General formulation of multilayer absorber
- ✓ Optimizing multilayer absorber is a process of minimizing the magnitude of the reflection coefficient
- ✓ It is achieved when the impedance of the absorber is matched to the closet value with Z_0 , 377Ω

- Input impedance of i-th layer

$$Z_{i+1} = Z_{ci} \frac{Z_{i-1} + Z_{ci} \tanh(\gamma_i d_i)}{Z_{ci} + Z_{i-1} \tanh(\gamma_i d_i)}$$

- Reflection coefficient

$$\Gamma = \frac{Z_{i+1} - Z_0}{Z_{i+1} + Z_0}$$

Z_i = Input impedance of i-th layer

Z_{i-1} = Input impedance of i-1th layer

Z_{ci} = Characteristic impedance of i-th layer

γ_i = Wave number of i-th layer

d_i = Thickness of i-th layer

III. Design and fabrication

Design

❖ Design of tapered honeycomb core radar absorbing structure

- Design parameter of tapered honeycomb core

Design parameter:
 H: Height
 t_u : Upper thickness
 t_l : Lower thickness
 L: Cell length

< (a) Design parameters of tapered honeycomb core, (b) simulation model of the tapered honeycomb core sandwich composites >

- Parametric study of thickness gradient honeycomb core

< Return loss simulation results of the tapered honeycomb core (a) cell length, (b) height, (c) lower thickness >

❖ Electromagnetic characteristic of designed radar absorbing structure

(a) Case #1

(b) Case #2

Parameter	L (mm)	H (mm)	t_u (mm)	t_l (mm)
Case #1	15	20	0.4	1.6
Case #2	15	20	1	1

< Return loss of honeycomb core sandwich structure with PEC > < Return loss of honeycomb core sandwich structure with PEC >

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Absorption} &= 1 - \text{Reflection} - \text{Transmission} \\
 &= 1 - |S_{11}|^2 - |S_{21}|^2
 \end{aligned}$$

< Electromagnetic characteristic of tapered honeycomb core (a) Case #1, (b) Case #2 >

Fabrication

❖ FDM 3D-Printing parameter of MWNTs dispersed PEEK

< Different printing result with nozzle temperature and Extrusion Multiplier >

< Melt Flow Index(MFI) of PEEK/CNT at 400 °C [13] >

< Percentile dimensional accuracy as a function of extrusion multiplier [14] >

Printing parameters	PEEK	PEEK/MWNTs
Nozzle temperature	400 °C	450 °C
Extrusion Multiplier	1	1.3
Chamber temperature	70 °C	70 °C
Printing speed	20 mm/s	20 mm/s
Layer thickness	10 mm	10 mm
Nozzle diameter	0.4 mm	0.4 mm

< Major printing parameter of PEEK based filaments >

[13] Marianna Rinaldi et al. Fused filament fabrication of polyetheretherketone/multiwalled carbonnanotube nanocomposites: the effect of thermally conductive nanometric filler on the printability and related properties, *Polym Int*, 2021; 70: 1080 – 1089

[14] László Lendvai et al. Experimental study on the effect of filament-extrusion rate on the structural, mechanical and thermal properties of material extrusion 3D-printed polylactic acid (PLA) products, *Progress in Additive Manufacturing* (2025) 10:619–629

IV. Results and discussion

Results and discussion

❖ Return loss of 3D-Printed tapered honeycomb core RAS

< Comparison of simulation results and printed RAS >

< Dimension of 3D-Printed RAS >

Parameter	t_{total} (mm)	L (mm)	H (mm)	t_u (mm)	t_l (mm)
Designed	20.6	15	20	0.4	1.6
3D-Printed	20.19	14.8	19.64	0.54	1.59

< Comparison of designed dimension and 3D-Printed dimension >

Results and discussion

❖ Mechanical properties of PEEK/MWNTs nanocomposites

- The annealing process was conducted at 260°C for 4 hours in a vacuum oven, followed by a cooling rate 1°C/min

Results and discussion

❖ Crystallinity of PEEK/MWNTs nanocomposites

< DSC analysis results (a) heating cycle, (b) cooling cycle >

Material	H_m	H_f	$(1-V_{MWNTs})$	X_c (%)
Neat PEEK	39.07	130	1	30.05
Annealed Neat PEEK	43.20	130	1	33.23
PEEK/MWNTs 12 wt%	31.74	130	0.912	26.87
Annealed PEEK/MWNTs 12 wt%	35.44	130	0.912	29.89

< The crystallization behavior of the PEEK and PEEK/MWNTs composites >

V. Conclusions

Conclusions

- In this study, electromagnetic wave absorbing PEEK/MWNTs nanocomposites filament were developed for radar absorbing structure
- Extrusion and FDM printing parameters were studied to extrude dimensionally consistent filaments and printed parts
- The thickness gradient tapered honeycomb core was designed and printed, and this structure significantly reduced surface reflection and enhanced broadband EM absorption
- MWNTs increased the tensile and flexural strength of PEEK and a 260 °C annealing process raised crystallinity, further improving mechanical performance
- In future work, we will compare the mechanical behavior of tapered honeycomb and uniform honeycomb core at the same density

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Thank you for your attention

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